

A proposal for a Geant4 physics list for radiotherapy optimised in physics performance and CPU time

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Abstract. We have studied each of the physics options that Geant4 offers to simulate an X-ray radiotherapy treatment with the aim of obtaining those that provide the best possible match to the experimental data of dose profiles and at the same time reduce the CPU time. The procedure has been repeated for two linac setups: an ELEKTA Versa HD with an Agility Multileaf Collimator using two nominal energies, 6 MV and 10 MV, both without flattening filter. After combining the results with those of a previous similar study of a 6 MV VARIAN Clinac 2100 C/D linac with flattening filter, we can propose a set of optimized Geant4 physics options of general use for radiotherapy simulation. Together with this, we have optimized the CPU time using several of the optimization techniques that GAMOS offers, reaching a reduction of several hundred times for each setup.

1. Introduction

Geant4 (Agostinelli 2003, Allison 2006, Allison 2016) is a particle Monte Carlo simulation code which can be used in many physics fields, including radiotherapy. Due to the variety of cases where Geant4 is used, it does not offer a default set of physics options, but it offers a wide spectrum of models, covering an energy range from eV to TeV. To help the user in selecting the best physics models for an application, Geant4 proposes the physics lists. A physics list is a set of physics models together with the model parameters that the Geant4 Collaboration considers optimal for the simulation in a given physics field. Together with this effort, in some physics fields, the Geant4 users have tested different physics options, through comparisons with experimental data and among themselves, with the same aim of finding the optimal physics options. Nevertheless, in the radiotherapy field, none of these two efforts have occurred: Geant4 does not offer any physics list tailored to this field and the effort from the users of comparing different physics options has been minimal.

If we focus on the physics relevant for the radiotherapy field, Geant4 offers three concurrent electromagnetic physics packages: *Standard*, *Livermore* and *Penelope*. Moreover, for one of the most important process, bremsstrahlung, it offers three different angular distributions for the *Livermore* package: *Tsai* (Tsai 1974, Tsai 1977), *Koch-Motz 2BN* and *Koch-Motz 2BS* (Koch 1959), one more for the *Standard* package: *dipBust* (Grichine 2013), plus the one used in the *Penelope* model. In a radiotherapy treatment, to simulate the many interactions that a charged particle suffers as it traverses matter, the model of choice in Geant4 is a condensed history model of class II (Berger 1963). The use of this model implies the need to define for the ionisation and bremsstrahlung processes a threshold below which secondary particles are not created, and moreover, this threshold should be different for each volume

region. On the other side, and different to other major Monte Carlo codes, Geant4 uses an integral approach for energy loss calculations, what avoids the need to define an energy value below which particles will be stopped and their energy considered as deposited energy in the medium. Nevertheless, it offers, through the user limits mechanism, the possibility to define such a threshold to try optimizing the CPU time. To simulate the Coulomb scattering in the condensed history approach, Geant4 offers three different models: *Urban* (Urban 2002), *Wentzel-VI* (Ivantchenko 2010) and *Goudsmit-Saunderson* (Goudsmit 1940, Incerti 2018).

Another set of parameters relevant for radiotherapy are those designed to optimize the length of each propagation step, so that the calculations of energy loss are precise enough while reducing the CPU time. These parameters depend on the range of the particle (the average distance that a particle travels until being stopped), and therefore of its energy and the material where it is being propagated. Similarly, concerning the Coulomb scattering, the step length is controlled by another set of parameters which depend on the range of the particle as well as on the distance to the volume boundaries, and which also have a different behaviour for the different scattering models, and even for each of the four different algorithms proposed to handle step limitation: *Minimal*, *UseDistanceToBoundary*, *UseSafety* and *UseSafetyPlus* (Apostolakis 2009, Ivantchenko 2010).

In this study we have optimized all the Geant4 electromagnetic physics models and parameters which are relevant for radiotherapy with the aim of obtaining a physics list which consumes the smallest CPU time while preserving the physics performance. In addition to this, we have also optimized the parameters of the techniques developed in GAMOS (Arce 2008, Arce 2014) that optimize the simulation efficiency. We have repeated this procedure for three different radiotherapy linac setups, with the aim of obtaining conclusions that can be generalized to other radiotherapy linacs.

2. Material and methods

The procedure we describe here to optimize the physics list in CPU time and in physics performance has already been done in a similar way for a 6 MV VARIAN Clinac 2100 C/D with the use of flattening filter (Arce 2018). In this work we repeat the procedure for two other linac setups: a 6 MV ELEKTA Versa HD with Agility multileaf collimator and without flattening filter, and the same linac with a different nominal energy, 10 MV. We have compared the options of all physics models and parameters to obtain values which may be of a general validity for any radiotherapy simulation with Geant4. The version of GAMOS used is 6.0.0, which is based on Geant4 version 10.04.p02, different to the version used before, GAMOS 5.1.0, based on Geant4 10.02, what increases the generalization of the results.

To validate a physics list, we check that it is the best possible one to reproduce the experimental data. But the first obstacle we found to optimize with precision the physics list is that the CPU time needed to obtain the requested precision sums up to several hundreds of thousands of hours for each setup. Therefore, we have used a mixed strategy in four steps:

- choose best-guess CPU optimization options to obtain approximate values of the beam parameters
- adjust one by one those optimization options that are quite independent of having a good fit to the experimental data
- optimize the linac beam and the Geant4 physics parameters to obtain the best possible match to the experimental data
- refine the CPU optimization options, repeating the optimization of those that may have some dependence with previous physics parameters

The techniques that belong to the second step are, by their order of optimization:

- Geometry and track navigation
- Physics cuts (production thresholds and user limits)
- Bremsstrahlung splitting technique
- Reusing of particles that reach the phantom
- Multiple scattering model
- Electromagnetic physics parameters

It may seem that the multiple scattering model choice is not independent of having a good fit to the experimental data, but, from the previous study we know that any of the three multiple scattering models provides good results, and that the Urban model is the fastest one. The electromagnetic physics parameters can also be considered independent of the experimental data matching, if we compare the dose distributions obtained with each combination of parameters with the results obtained with the most precise parameters. In any case, it should be remembered that this second step is done after the beam parameters has been chosen by a fast matching to the experimental data, and that the final choice of parameters is confirmed, or slightly modified, in the fourth step.

Once we have optimised these parameters, we optimized:

- Bremsstrahlung angular distribution
- Beam parameters: energy, width and dispersion angle

These parameters have a strong correlation among themselves, and therefore there are multiple combinations of them that give similar results. To do their adjustment we have used an iterative approach, until we get the combination that best matches the experimental data.

To adjust the simulation to the experimental data we have used equivalent sets of data for both energies. The aperture field sizes used are 2x2 cm², 3x3 cm², 5x5 cm², 10x10 cm², 20x20 cm², 30x30 cm² and 40x40 cm². For each field we have measured the Percentage Depth Dose profile curve plus for each of the two perpendicular directions five Cross Profiles curves at peak depth (1.5 cm for 6 MV and 2 cm for 10 MV) and depths of 5 cm, 10 cm, 20 cm and 30 cm. For the PDD the separation between measurements is 2 mm and for Cross Profiles also 2 mm, except in the zone of the penumbra, where we have taken a measurement each 0.5 mm.

The only case where we have made a significant change of the methodology with respect to the previous study (Arce 2018) is the optimization of some of the electromagnetic physics parameters. These parameters are those that use energy loss and multiple scattering models to limit the step length, so that the desired precision can be reached, namely:

- Energy loss limits of the step length:
 - *RoverRange*: $step_length \leq range * RoverRange$, where *range* is the average distance that a particle can travel in a medium with the current energy
 - *FinalRange*: makes a unique final step when particle range < *FinalRange*
- Multiple scattering limits of the step length:
 - *RangeFactor*: when a particle is generated or enters a new volume $step_length < max(range, \lambda) * RangeFactor$, where λ is the first transport mean free path
 - *GeomFactor*: when a particle enters a new volume $step_length < GeomFactor * dist$, where *dist* is the distance to the next volume boundary in the direction of the particle

- *Skin*: limits the step length when a particle is about to leave a volume, $step_length < (Skin-1)*\lambda_{el}$, where λ_{el} is the elastic mean free path

While in the previous work we have optimized each parameter independently, we opted here for a more integral approach, trying to find a combination of these parameters that offers optimal physics performance while optimising the CPU time consumption. As recommended by the Geant4 experts (Mihaly Novak, private communication) we used the *UseSafetyPlus* step limitation algorithm as the optimal one in physics performance. Together with it, we selected as optimal parameters *RoverRange* = 0.01, *FinalRange* = 0.01 mm, *RangeFactor* = 0.01, *GeomFactor* = 2.5 and *Skin* = 3. To study the many possible combinations of these parameters we have first set the rule of not using very different values of two parameters that would make that one of them is almost never applied (for example if we limit *RoverRange* to a very low value, setting *RangeFactor* to a value close to 1, may have no impact). Instead of making a full calculation of the dose profiles for several tens or hundreds of parameter combinations, we have classified these combinations by the average number of steps that electrons make (what can be quickly calculated with good precision). We have then made the dose calculation only for a few combinations of the parameters that are separated in this classification table. By comparing the dose distributions with the ones obtained with the optimal configuration, we found in a first phase the parameter combination that have the smallest CPU time consumption while having a negligible difference in dose. In a second phase we tested a few other parameter combinations that have a similar number of electron steps that the one selected in the first phase, to refine the optimization of CPU time performance. Finally, we changed the step limit algorithm to each of the other three available ones and repeated the optimization.

3. Results

3.1. CPU time optimization

For all techniques, except where explicitly mentioned, the results are given for 1.E8-1.E9 initial electrons with energy 8. MeV or 13. MeV, 0 beam width and 0 beam dispersion angles, jaws and multileaf collimator field apertures configuring a 10x10 cm² field, using *EWBS* with splitting number 50 and reusing 50 times the particles that reach the phantom. The electromagnetic physics models used are the *Standard* ones, with default parameters.

Before optimizing the parameters, we have optimized the simulation geometry and the navigation inside it:

- We have defined a global mother volume fitted to the accelerator + phantom components
- We have killed all particles that exit the target block by its sides or back plane. This only kills about 6% of the tracks and saves a negligible percentage of the CPU time.
- Instead of defining a full 3-dimensional voxel phantom we have defined a water volume and created inside voxels only in the XZ and YZ planes which include the linac beam axis, as these are the only planes where experimental data has been taken. To automatically create this geometry and score the dose in it, we use the GAMOS geometry builder *GmCrossPhantomGeometry*. This reduces the CPU time spent in the phantom navigation by a factor 1.9 in the 6 MV setup and 2.5 in the 10 MV setup.

- The option in the Geant4 regular navigation algorithm of skipping contiguous voxels that have the same material in spares an extra 8% of the CPU time in the phantom for the 6 MV setup and 17% in the 10 MV setup.

We show in Table 1 the results obtained for each parameter optimized for the three setups studied, together with the CPU time savings.

Table 1. Values of the parameters of the different optimization options used and CPU time spared

	VARIAN 6 MV	ELEKTA 6 MV	ELEKTA 10 MV
Production cuts in linac	See Table 1 of (Arce 2018)	See Table 2	See Table 2
CPU gain	25%	25%	25%
Production cuts in phantom	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
CPU gain	6%	7%	5%
Bremsstrahlung splitting	BiasPrimaryOnly=0 BiasOnlyOnce = 0	BiasPrimaryOnly=0 BiasOnlyOnce = 0	BiasPrimaryOnly=0 BiasOnlyOnce = 0
	DimX = 100 mm DimY = 500 mm	DimX = 300 mm DimY = 300 mm	DimX = 300 mm DimY = 300 mm
	EWBS N=100	EWBS N=50	EWBS N=50
	5.0	4.1	2.4
Particle reuse in phantom	N = 100	N = 50	N=50
CPU gain	48	14	12
Electromagnetic physics model set	Standard	Standard	Standard
Multiple scattering model	Urban	Urban	Urban
Electromagnetic physics parameters	See Table 4 of (Arce 2018)	See Table 3	See Table 3
CPU gain	- 10%	-34%	-20%

Table 2. Optimized production thresholds for the different components of the linac head

	VARIAN 6 MV		ELEKTA 6 MV / 10 MV	
Geometry region	Production threshold for e-'s (mm)	Production threshold for gammas (mm)	Production threshold for e-'s (mm)	Production threshold for gammas (mm)
Target	1	10	0.1	3
Primary collimator	0.1	10	0.1	1
Flattening filter	1	10	--	--
Monitor	1	10	0.3	10
Shielding	1	10	–	–
Wedge	–	–	3	100
Jaws	0.3	1	0.1	0.3
MLC			0.1	0.3
Outside linac components	10	10	1	1

3.2. Electromagnetic parameters

The electromagnetic parameters are optimized using the Urban multiple scattering model, as from (Arce 2018) we expect it to be the fastest one and the physics results to be independent of the multiple scattering model. As the behaviour of the different multiple scattering models may be related to the internal step limit parameters, we checked after the full optimization that the physics performance does not change with the final parameters, and we also checked that the CPU time is still optimal with the Urban model.

In a first step we optimize three of these step-limit parameters: *RoverRange*, *FinalRange* and *RangeFactor*, leaving the other two to their default values, i.e. *GeometryFactor* = 2.5, *Skin* = 1. As commented above, there are many combinations that give similar results. The chosen values, optimized in CPU and at the same time not producing any physics performance deterioration when compared with the “optimal” values are the same for both linac energies: *RoverRange* = 0.2, *FinalRange* = 0.1 and *RangeFactor* = 0.05. With these values, the changes of the *GeometryFactor* or the *Skin* have only a negligible influence in the CPU time, so we kept the selected values. Using this set of values, the other three step limit algorithms: *UseSafety*, *UseDistanceToBoundary* and *Minimal*, reduce the CPU time only a few % but have a non-negligible influence in the dose.

For the other electromagnetic physics parameters, we also leave the values by default in the Standard physics models, as their change does not improve the CPU time consumption. These values are: linear loss limit = 0.01, lowest kinetic energy for electrons and positron in the

energy loss tables = 100 eV, limit below which linear interpolation is used to calculate energy loss = 10 keV and number of bins per decade of energy for the energy loss and range tables = 20.

These optimized parameters increase the CPU time with respect to the time obtained when using the default parameters of the Standard electromagnetic models, by a factor of 34% for the 6 MV setup and 20% for the 10 MV setup. The main reason is that we had to lower the *FinalRange* parameter, as the default value of 1 produces some small, but visible, differences.

Table 3. Optimized electromagnetic physics parameters

Parameter name	Precise value	Default Value
<i>mscStepLimit</i>	UseSafetyPlus	UseDistanceToBoundary
<i>RoverRange</i>	0.2	0.2
<i>FinalRange</i>	0.1	1.
<i>RangeFactor</i>	0.05	0.04
<i>GeomFactor</i>	2.5	2.5
<i>Skin</i>	3	1
<i>lowKinE</i>	1 keV	1 keV
<i>binsDecade</i>	20	7
<i>linLossLimit</i>	0.01	0.01

3.3. Beam parameters and Bremsstrahlung angular distribution

Before fitting the beam parameters, we have corrected the non-horizontality of the data measurements and their lateral displacement from the beam central axis. The horizontality is compatible with 0, and the average lateral displacement is in average 0.3 mm, with values bigger than 0.7 mm in only 5% of the cases, and a maximum value of 1.2 mm.

The first step of the beam parameters fit is aimed to obtain the beam energy by using the Percentage Depth Dose profiles. With enough Monte Carlo events to reach a dose bin precision of 0.5%, similar to the uncertainty of the experimental data, we can test energies that differ by only 0.1 MeV. Our first surprise when fitting the small aperture fields ($\leq 10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$) is that the best fit is obtained with an energy of 8. MeV for the 6 MV configuration and 13.1 MeV for the 10 MV one. But these are indeed the expected energies, as the vendor confirms that when the flattening filter is not used the energy is increased around 30% with the aim of making the PDD's with and without flattening filter as similar as possible (the presence of the flattening filter produces a harder X-ray beam).

In the case of the PDD's of bigger aperture fields, the energy that best matches the dose slope after the peak increases with the field aperture. For the 6 MV setup the energy that best fits the slope varies from 8 MeV up to 9 MeV for the $40 \times 40 \text{ cm}^2$, and for the 10 MV one it varies from 13.1 MeV up to 17.5 MeV. It must be taken into account that if we divide the data and the Monte Carlo the difference of the slopes is only about 1 % for the 6 MV setup and 2 %

for the 10 MV setup, and it can only be clearly seen thanks to the high statistics we use. After investigating different linac material compositions, we think that this change of energy is due to a wrong energy-angle distribution of the gamma particles produced by bremsstrahlung.

The beam aperture angles have a strong correlation with the beam energy, and with the selection of the bremsstrahlung angular distributions. For both linac energies we found that the best match is found using the Tsai distribution in the case of the smallest fields, but Koch-Motz 2BS in the case of the biggest fields, which is the same result as the one obtained in (Arce 2018). Using 8 MeV we get an optimal fit for all aperture fields with a bidimensional Gaussian aperture angle distribution with $\sigma = 0^\circ$ in the in-plane direction and 1.5° in the cross-plane direction for the 6 MV setup, and 0.5° and 1.5° for the 10 MV setup (the direction of the angle with bigger values is the one in the plane where the electron beam suffers a 90° turn, as expected). The dose distributions are quite independent of a small beam width, therefore we use the one given by the vendor: a 2D Gaussian distribution with FWHM = 1 mm. Using the energies that best match the PDD of the $40 \times 40 \text{ cm}^2$ fields, we are not able to get good cross-profiles matching with any of the bremsstrahlung angular distributions, while with the lower energies the matching is quite good. Several of the optimised Monte Carlo dose profiles compared to the experimental data can be seen in figures 1 to 10.

Figure 1. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the PDD distributions for $3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$, $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$, $20 \times 20 \text{ cm}^2$, $40 \times 40 \text{ cm}^2$ fields using the optimised physics options, for the 6 MV setup

Figure 2. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the PDD distributions for 3x3 cm², 10x10 cm², 20x20 cm², 40x40 cm² fields using the optimised physics options, for the 10 MV setup

Figure 3. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 3x3 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 6 MV setup

Figure 4. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 10x10 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 6 MV setup

Figure 5. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 20x20 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 6 MV setup

Figure 6. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 40x40 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 6 MV setup

Figure 7. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 3x3 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 10 MV setup

Figure 8. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 10x10 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 10 MV setup

Figure 9. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 20x20 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 10 MV setup

Figure 10. Comparison between the data and Monte Carlo of the cross-profile distributions for 40x40 cm² fields, in the in-plane (right) and cross-plane (left) directions using the optimised physics options, for the 10 MV setup

3.4. Geant4 official electromagnetic physics lists

We have also tested if the Geant4 electromagnetic physics constructors provided with the Geant4 code are suitable for radiotherapy simulation. We have created physics list using the physics constructors: *G4EmStandard*, *G4EmStandard_option1*, *G4EmStandard_option2*, *G4EmStandard_option3*, *G4EmStandard_option4*, *G4EmLowEPPhysics*, *G4EmLivermore* and *G4EmPenelope*. We have not tested *G4EmStandard_GS*, *G4EmStandard_WVI* nor *G4EmStandard_SS* because they are designed just to test the different multiple scattering models (what we have already done) and, moreover, the last two are one order of magnitude or two slower than the others.

G4EmStandard, *G4EmStandard_option1* do not match the experimental data because they use the *dipBust* bremsstrahlung angular distribution. *G4EmPenelope* also offers a bad matching because the Penelope bremsstrahlung model used in our Geant4 version is not adequate. *G4EmStandard_option2* produces a valley in the centre of the cross profiles dose curves, because it uses too big values of the parameters that limit the step length. Also, *G4EmLowEPPhysics* produces a small valley, although the only relevant difference is the use of the LowEP Compton model. *G4EmStandard_option3*, *G4EmStandard_option4* and *G4EmLivermore* offer a match to the experimental data as good as our optimized physics list, within statistical fluctuations.

These three last physics lists are though quite slower than our optimized physics list, specially *G4EmStandard_option4*, which is more than twice slower. For this reason, we cannot recommend them. Table 5 summarizes the behaviour of the Geant4 physics lists together with the ratio of CPU time with respect to our optimized physics list for the 6MV and the 10 MV setups.

Table 4. Behaviour in matching to the experimental data of the Geant4 official electromagnetic physics lists, and CPU time of each physics list divided by CPU time of our optimized physics list

Physics List	Fit to exper. Data	6 MV: CPU time / optimized PL	10 MV: CPU time / optimized PL
<i>Our optimized PL</i>	OK	1	1
<i>G4EmStandard</i>	BAD (dipBust Bremss. ang. distr.)	1.14	1.17
<i>G4EmStandard_option1</i>	BAD (dipBust Bremss. ang. distr.)	0.35	0.38
<i>G4EmStandard_option2</i>	BAD (too big step length)	0.99	0.98
<i>G4EmStandard_option3</i>	OK	1.27	1.23
<i>G4EmStandard_option4</i>	OK	2.37	2.43
<i>G4EmLowEPPhysics</i>	BAD (LowEP Compton)	1.47	1.43
<i>G4EmLivermore</i>	OK	1.58	1.58
<i>G4EmPenelope</i>	BAD (Penelope Bremss. ang. distr.)	1.22	1.13

4. Summary and conclusions

We have made a precise comparison of the Monte Carlo simulation of an ELEKTA Versa HD X-ray radiotherapy linac with the experimental data of dose profiles using two configurations: 6 MV and 10 MV, both without flattening filter. The different electromagnetic physics options have been optimised to have the minimum CPU time consumption without affecting the physics performance. Together with this we have tuned the CPU optimization options that Geant4 offers plus several more than have been developed within the GAMOS framework.

By comparing the optimal physics options of the two setups and those options for a different accelerator, a 6 MV VARIAN Clinac 2100 C/D with flattening filter we have obtained the following optimised physics models and parameters:

- Standard electromagnetic physics models
- Electromagnetic energy loss parameters:
 - o /process/eLoss/binsPerDecade 20
 - o /process/eLoss/StepFunction 0.2 0.1
 - o /process/em/lowestElectronEnergy 1 keV
- Urban multiple scattering model
- Multiple scattering parameters
 - o /process/msc/StepLimit UseSafetyPlus
 - o /process/msc/RangeFactor 0.05
 - o /process/msc/GeomFactor 2.5
 - o /process/msc/Skin 1

- Bremsstrahlung angular distribution: Tsai if the field is smaller or equal than 20x20 cm², Koch-Motz 2BS if the field is bigger than 20x20 cm²

These physics options are included in the newly created GAMOS physics list named *RTPhysics*.

Together with these options we recommend using the following CPU time optimization options:

- Define a world with dimensions fitted to the accelerator + phantom components
- Do not create a full 3-dimensional matrix of voxels, but voxelise only the planes where experimental data has been taken. If the planes are only the central XZ and YZ planes, we recommend the use of the GAMOS *GmCrossPhantomGeometry* geometry builder
- Use the regular navigation to track particles in the phantom, with the option of skipping contiguous voxels that have the same material (default option)
- Optimize the production thresholds in the linac components. Although the optimized values depend on the linac geometry, and therefore no general values can be given, the values obtained in this work and (Arce 2018) can be used as a reference. We recommend the use of the utility in GAMOS to calculate the optimized values in all volumes and for all particles with a single job
- Optimize the production threshold in the phantom. We consider than a value of 1/5 of the voxel dimension is enough, although a safer value can be 1/10, as the CPU time difference with these two values is negligible.
- Use GAMOS bremsstrahlung splitting technique EWBS, with a splitting number of 50, a splitting field bigger around 50 cm than the beam aperture field and the options *BiasPrimaryOnly=1* and *BiasOnlyOnce=1* (default options)
- Reuse 50 times the gammas that reach the phantom, mirroring the tracks in X and Y (in case your field is symmetric with respect to the X=0 and Y=0 planes)

Using the above optimisations, we get a good match to the experimental data, well below the precisions recommended by the ICRU Report 42: 2% dose-difference and 2 mm distance-to-agreement gamma index (Low 1998).

When all optimization options are used, the CPU time efficiency improvement for a 10x10 cm² field with respect to the default options is approximately: 525 for the 6MV VARIAN Clinac 2100 C/D with flattering filter, 350 for the 6 MV ELEKTA Versa HD without flattening filter and 225 for the 10 MV ELEKTA Versa HD without flattening filter.

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